

THE ROLE OF FORENSIC MEDICINE IN TRAINING QUALIFIED DOCTORS IN THE FUTURE

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ANNOTATION

In connection with the introduction of the training of general practitioners, "the targeted tasks of teaching forensic medicine in undergraduate studies have been changed. If earlier a student was considered as a specialist in future forensic medicine, then recently lectures and practical classes in forensic medicine have been aimed at the specifics of the activities of a general practitioner.

Key words: General practitioner, forensic medical examination.

In the previous period, according to the current legislation, the possibility of involvement of doctors of various fields in procedural actions related to forensic medicine (forensic medical expertise, inspection of the place where the body was found, etc.) was the main purpose of teaching the science of forensic medicine to students. Based on current legal documents, this issue has been put on the back burner. Therefore, at the moment, the main purpose of the education of forensic science at the bachelor's level is to master the features of providing medical assistance in cases that will later have forensic expertise by future doctors.

According to official data, in one-third of the forensic examinations conducted in recent years, corpses were taken from mortuary institutions, and at the same time, medical history data served as an object of examination during the examination process. In more than 60% of forensic medical examinations of living persons, the victims received various forms of medical care and then underwent an expert examination.

Taking into account the situation, changes and objects that serve as a source of evidence in forensic examination for obvious reasons, the characteristics of their initial state and the dynamics of their change are of great importance. Consequently, the deficiencies made by the doctors in these areas cannot be eliminated by the expert and ultimately lead to the failure to solve the tasks set before the forensic examination. When general practitioners find traces of injuries or similar illegal actions in patients seeking medical help, they should describe these changes, taking into account the objectives of the forensic

medical examination, which will be appointed later. For example, when cysts are detected, their location, color, shape, size, condition of the surrounding tissue, location, shape, size, direction, presence of a coating and its level in relation to the surrounding skin, condition of the surrounding structure, and location, shape, size, edges of the wound in wounds, tips, edge wall, bottom should be detailed in medical documents. They are very important for solving the issues of the weapon that caused the injury, the mechanism and time of the injury, and determining the severity of the injury in forensic examination. After all, after providing medical assistance, after a certain period of time, the expert will not be able to obtain this information. After 10-15 days, swelling and swelling may disappear without a trace, the primary surgeon cannot answer these questions regarding the subsequent scar.

In the cases mentioned above, failure of general practitioners to perform their duties properly will have a negative impact on the quality of the expertise that will be appointed later and the range of issues that can be resolved in it. This, in turn, is the cause of reasonable and serious objections to the activities of doctors by the law enforcement agencies conducting the investigation and investigation of the committed crime.

Thus, acquisition of knowledge and skills in the field of forensic medicine by a general practitioner ensures the provision of quality, complete medical care in cases of forensic medical expertise.

References:

1. Гийсов З.А. – Суд тиббиёти. Т., 2018.
2. А.И.Искандаров, Д.Р.Қўлдошев – Суд тиббиёти. Т., 2009.
3. И.И.Бахриев, Д.Д.Джалалов. – Қон, сперма ва сочларни суд тиббиётига оид текшириш. Талабалар учун услубий қўлланма. Т., 2001.
4. Giyasov, Z. A., Dehkanov, M. A., & Hakimov, S. A. (2021). Analysis of commission forensic examinations related to the provision of medical care to children.
5. Гиясов, З. А., Назарова, М. М., Бахриев, И. И., Хакимов, С. А., & Вафоев, З. Б. (2019). К вопросу экспертной оценки медицинской помощи детям и подросткам.
6. Khakimov, S. A. (2023). Clinical Morphological Forensic Medical Aspects of Postasphyctic Cases. International Journal Of Health Systems And Medical Sciences, 2(3), 97-101.
7. Гиясов, З. А., & Хакимов, С. А. (2022). Постасфиктик ҳолатларнинг гендер жиҳатлари.

8. Хакимов, С. А. (2022). Турли жинс вакилларида тугалланмаган асфиксиянинг суд тиббий жиҳатлари.
9. Seifullaeva, G. A., Khvan, O. I., Karimova, F. D., Khakimov, S. A., & Eshanov, D. S. (2022). Defects In The Provision Of Medical Care In Obstetric Practice. Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results, 3894-3897.
10. Hakimov, S. A., Baxriyev, I. I., Sultanov, S. B., & Gulyamov, D. E. (2022). Sud tibbiyoti amaliyotida postasfiktik holatlarni baholashning ahamiyati.
11. Giyasov, Z. A., Hakimov, S. A., Makhsumkhonov, K. A., Gulyamov, D. E., & Suleymanov, A. A. (2022). Gender Aspects of Postaphyxia Conditions.
12. Giyasov, Z. A., & Khakimov, S. A. (2021). Features of Postasphyctic Conditions In Children And Adolescents. International Journal Of Medical Science And Clinical Research Studies, 1(7), 211-214.
13. Giyasov, Z. A., & Khakimov, S. A. (2021). Forensic Description Of Cases Of Noletal Asphyxia. The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research, 3(08), 58-68.
14. 16. Hakimov, S. A. (2021, February). Amnesia In Postasphyctic Cases. In International Scientific and Current Research Conferences (pp. 37-38).

